

How Can AI Support ESL Writing Without Encouraging Metacognitive Laziness?

A Structured Use of ChatGPT via Fobizz in a
Secondary School Writing Task

Master Thesis

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Abstract

This master's thesis examines how a structured use of artificial intelligence (AI) can support English as a Second Language (ESL) writing in secondary education without encouraging metacognitive laziness. The project grew out of classroom practice and explores how guided interaction with ChatGPT can help students think about their own thinking while writing.

Grounded in theories of metacognition, cognitive offloading, dialogic feedback, and desirable difficulties, the study implements a three-step writing process: students first handwrite their drafts, then type and expand them, and finally use ChatGPT via Fobizz to receive feedback that they must accept, adapt, or reject with justification. Successive drafts, short reflection notes, and open-ended questionnaires provide insight into how students plan, monitor, and evaluate their writing.

The results show that when AI feedback is embedded within a teacher-structured framework that demands explanation and accountability, learners engage more deeply with their own revision process. They become more reflective, clearer in expression, and more confident in making choices about their texts.

The thesis concludes with practical implications for classroom use: prompts should invite reasoning, not simple correction; AI feedback should remain dialogic and reflective; and writing tasks should align with Lehrplan 21 competencies on strategy use and self-regulation. Overall, the study offers a concrete example of how AI can be integrated responsibly into school-based ESL writing to strengthen, not replace, students' metacognitive awareness.

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1. Introduction

1.1 Background and Relevance

In recent years, artificial intelligence (AI) has become a fast-moving force in education. One tool that has gained particular attention is ChatGPT, a large language model (LLM) developed by OpenAI that can assist students with writing, research, and revision. While many educators recognize the potential of this tool, others express concern about its impact on student learning, particularly on higher-order thinking skills such as self-reflection, planning, and critical engagement. Unlike earlier technological innovations, AI is developing so rapidly that schools and teachers often struggle to adapt effectively.

As AI tools have become widely available, many students began using them to generate entire texts, often copying and pasting the output without engaging in proofreading or revision. This behavior makes an already complex skill even more challenging. Writing has long been recognized as one of the most demanding abilities in foreign language learning, as “writing is one of the most complex language skills to master because it requires the integration of multiple components such as idea generation, organization, language use, and revision” (Vula, Tyfekçi, & Biblekaj, 2024, p. 96). In the Swiss context, the *Lehrplan 21* defines writing (*Schreiben*) as a core competence alongside listening, reading, and speaking (Deutschschweizer Erziehungsdirektoren-Konferenz [D-EDK], 2016). Yet in practice, many students continue to struggle with planning, revising, and reflecting on their texts. These difficulties highlight the need for explicit strategy use and metacognitive engagement in the writing process, as “learners’ self-regulated learning becomes critical to their academic success, affecting how they plan, monitor, and evaluate their learning in online environments” (Jin et al., 2023, p. 2).

This study is based on a developmental classroom project (*Entwicklungsarbeit*) conducted in secondary-school English lessons. The writing process was designed and implemented as a structured sequence in which students first produced a handwritten draft, then revised it in Word, and finally used ChatGPT via the educational platform Fobizz to reflect on and improve their texts. Since ChatGPT itself is officially restricted to users aged 18 and above, direct classroom access was not permitted.

Fobizz, a German educational platform developed for teachers, provides a range of pedagogical tools that integrate AI into teaching practice, including functions for lesson planning, feedback generation, and worksheet creation. The platform enables teachers to design interactive, secure, and data-protection-compliant learning environments. Within this study, Fobizz served as a safeguarded interface to ChatGPT, allowing students to access AI-generated feedback under controlled and age-appropriate conditions. Classroom materials, student texts, and open-ended questionnaire data form the empirical basis of this research.

From a pedagogical perspective, digital tools can both support and challenge learning. The internet has transformed how students access knowledge, shifting the teacher's role from transmitter to facilitator. Generative AI represents a further shift because it can produce entire texts autonomously, raising essential questions about how student autonomy and metacognitive skills can be preserved.

Against this background, the present thesis investigates whether a structured use of ChatGPT can support or hinder metacognitive engagement, focusing on how students plan, monitor, and reflect on their writing. The aim is to contribute to the current debate on AI in education by showing how carefully designed instructional frameworks can integrate new technologies into classroom practice without undermining essential learning processes.

1.2 Professional Context and Problem Definition

The project was carried out at a secondary school in the Canton of Zurich, where the author teaches English, Media/Informatics, and Religion–Culture–Ethics. The school places a strong emphasis on digital competence and data protection, providing a relevant context for examining the pedagogical use of artificial intelligence in classroom learning. As part of this environment, the author initiated a classroom-based exploration of how generative AI could be integrated into English writing instruction in a structured and reflective manner. Since this master's thesis represents an "*Entwicklungsarbeit*", the following section outlines the institutional and pedagogical context that informed the design and implementation of the project.

At the beginning of the 2024–2025 school year, small-scale writing projects were conducted using Microsoft CoPilot in Units 1 and 2. These pilot activities enabled students to use AI for planning and revision and demonstrated that guided digital feedback could enhance awareness of structure and accuracy. However, institutional restrictions soon emerged. Because ChatGPT is officially classified as 18+, students were not permitted to access it on school devices, and by late October 2024, the CoPilot functions were also disabled for student accounts. Extending the licenses to include student access was considered financially unfeasible.

In response, the author searched for a legally compliant and pedagogically appropriate alternative and identified **Fobizz**, a German educational platform providing GDPR-compliant access to ChatGPT. After consultation with the school's ICT department and colleagues at PH Zürich, the free version of Fobizz was introduced for classroom writing activities. These initial sessions provided the empirical basis for the present study.

When the project was later expanded, the school management decided to re-examine Fobizz with regard to data protection and institutional policy. In May 2025, the use of the platform was temporarily suspended until formal approval by the *Schulpflege* (school board). Because the meeting was postponed and the summer holidays intervened, official permission was only granted in September 2025. This delay limited the amount of data that could be collected but also illustrated how pedagogical innovation is shaped by administrative regulation.

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his professional situation defines one of the core practical problems addressed in this thesis: how AI-assisted writing tools can be implemented ethically, securely, and pedagogically meaningfully within the strict data-protection framework of Swiss secondary education.

1.3 Research question and objectives

This study examines how a teacher-structured integration of ChatGPT via the educational platform Fobizz can support English as a Second Language (ESL) writing without encouraging cognitive offloading. The intervention was embedded within a guided three-step writing process that required students to handwrite, type, and then revise their texts using AI-generated feedback. Each phase involved explicit reflection prompts and teacher mediation to ensure that the use of AI remained reflective rather than substitutive. The focus lies on how students plan, monitor, and evaluate their writing decisions within this structured pedagogical design.

Research question

How can a structured integration of ChatGPT via Fobizz support metacognitive engagement in ESL writing without encouraging cognitive offloading?

Objectives

1. To design and implement a teacher-guided three-step writing workflow that fosters metacognitive engagement.
2. To collect and analyze writing artifacts and student reflections to identify how learners plan, monitor, and evaluate their work.
3. To derive practice-oriented implications for the responsible and meaningful integration of AI in secondary ESL writing instruction.

2. Theoretical Framework and Literature Review

This chapter provides the theoretical foundation of the study. It begins by outlining writing as a complex cognitive and metacognitive process in English as a Second Language (ESL) learning. On this basis, it introduces key concepts such as metacognitive laziness, cognitive offloading, feedback literacy, and desirable difficulty, which help to analyze how AI tools may support or hinder students' thinking. These perspectives frame the central question of how AI can function not as a shortcut, but as a scaffold for reflective and autonomous writing.

2.1 Writing as a complex skill in ESL

Writing in a second language is widely recognized as one of the most demanding skills to master. Unlike oral communication, where meaning can be negotiated through interaction, writing requires sustained control of linguistic form, coherence, and idea development. For many secondary students, the challenge lies not only in grammatical accuracy or vocabulary use but also in the ability to generate, organize, and refine ideas across multiple stages of composition. As Davoodifard (2022) explains, the process-oriented view of writing “considers not only the linguistic aspects of writing but also the cognitive and metacognitive aspects that involve the necessary phases a student goes through to produce a text. These phases can include brainstorming, planning, generating ideas, and revising and reflecting on one’s own work” (p. 2).

From the teacher’s perspective, writing instruction therefore involves balancing language development with cognitive and metacognitive support. Students must be guided not only in using accurate grammar and vocabulary but also in learning how to think through a writing task, how to plan, monitor, and evaluate their own text. At the same time, the writing context itself, particularly when tied to formal assessment, adds another layer of complexity. As Deane et al. (2008, as cited in Davoodifard, 2022, p. 2) emphasize, “being a complex cognitive ability, writing can pose additional affective and cognitive demands on language learners when performing under assessment conditions.”

Research shows that many students struggle to transfer writing strategies learned in class to exam contexts, where time constraints and cognitive pressure limit revision

and reflection (Deane et al., 2008; Davoodifard, 2022). To address these challenges, scholars highlight the importance of instructional frameworks that mirror authentic writing conditions and integrate planning, composing, and revising within realistic time frames (Davoodifard, 2022).

Within this perspective, artificial intelligence can function as a scaffolding tool that supports cognitive and metacognitive activity without replacing the learner's decision-making. AI-generated feedback may prompt idea generation, highlight revision possibilities, and encourage critical evaluation of language choices. When used reflectively, such tools can reinforce the cognitive dimensions of writing identified by Davoodifard (2022), helping learners remain mentally active and engaged throughout the process.

Understanding writing as a metacognitively demanding skill therefore provides the basis for examining how new technologies, such as AI, may either support or undermine learners' engagement in these mental processes.

2.2 Metacognitive laziness and cognitive offloading

Fan et al. (2025) define *metacognitive laziness* as the tendency of learners to avoid deliberate cognitive effort: "Learners may begin to habitually avoid deliberate cognitive effort, a phenomenon we refer to as metacognitive laziness" (p. 18). They explain that their definition "aligns with prior theoretical frameworks by Risko and Gilbert (2016) and Alter et al. (2007). Risko and Gilbert's (2016) concept of *cognitive offloading* highlights how reliance on external resources can diminish learners' engagement in metacognitive processes, leading to a habitual reduction in internal cognitive monitoring and self-regulation" (as cited in Fan et al., 2025, p. 18). This understanding connects closely to findings by Oppenheimer, Alter, Epley, and Eyre (2007), who demonstrated that metacognitive experiences of difficulty or disfluency activate more analytic reasoning processes. In the context of AI-assisted learning, this suggests that carefully designed cognitive strain, such as having to revise or reflect on AI-generated feedback, may help students overcome automaticity and engage in deeper, more reflective thinking.

Offloading is not a new phenomenon, students have always relied on notes, dictionaries, or calculators, but generative AI has intensified this tendency. Gerlich (2025) supports this concern, reporting “a significant negative correlation between the frequent use of AI tools and critical thinking abilities, mediated by the phenomenon of cognitive offloading” (p. 14). This issue is directly relevant to my project. In my own classroom, I have observed that when students use ChatGPT without structure, they often copy and paste outputs without revision or reflection. The staged process I designed was intended to counteract this habit and reintroduce planning and monitoring steps into writing.

Developing such habits of reflection requires a learning environment where feedback serves as an active dialogue rather than a one-way transmission.

2.3 Feedback as dialogue and feedback literacy

Feedback remains one of the most powerful influences on learning outcomes, yet it is often misunderstood and underutilized. In many English classrooms, feedback still occurs primarily as teacher correction after a writing task, frequently delivered too late for students to apply it effectively. Research shows that many learners continue to perceive feedback mainly as information transmitted by teachers rather than as a process of active engagement that includes peer and self-assessment (McLean, Bond, & Nicholson, 2015; Price et al., 2011, as cited in Molloy, Boud, & Henderson, 2020, pp. 528–529).

Molloy et al. (2020) propose a learning-centered view in which “students’ ability to understand, utilize and benefit from feedback processes” (p. 528) becomes a core competence rather than a by-product of assessment. Their framework identifies a range of learner capabilities, such as seeking information, interpreting criteria, managing emotions, and translating feedback into future action. This reconceptualization shifts attention from teachers’ comments to learners’ active involvement in making sense of feedback and applying it purposefully. Similarly, Carless and Boud (2018) define *student feedback literacy* as “the understandings, capacities and dispositions needed to make sense of information and use it to enhance

work or learning strategies” (p. 2). Both perspectives frame feedback as an interactive and dialogic process grounded in reflection, interpretation, and agency.

Within this theoretical context, the present study adopts a dialogic perspective on feedback, emphasizing continuous interaction between learners, teachers, and technological tools. The structured three-stage writing process—handwriting, digital self-editing, and AI-assisted revision—positions feedback as an iterative dialogue that promotes metacognitive engagement. Students are guided to evaluate AI-generated suggestions, make informed choices, and justify revisions, thereby transforming feedback from passive reception into active decision-making. In this model, artificial intelligence functions as one participant in a broader feedback conversation, expanding opportunities for reflection while maintaining learners’ responsibility for authorship and meaning construction.

Differentiated instruction further complements this framework by addressing variation in learners’ readiness, interest, and learning profiles. As Subban (2006) explains, drawing on Tomlinson (2000a, 2001a, 2003), differentiation “avoids the pitfalls of the one-size-fits-all curriculum” and provides opportunities for all students to perform at their best (p. 939). It draws on research into cognitive diversity and multiple intelligences (Tomlinson, 2001c; Tomlinson & Kalbfleisch, 1998; Lawrence-Brown, 2004; Tuttle, 2000) and allows adjustment of content, process, and product to individual learning needs. Recent work by Han et al. (2023) extends this principle to digital contexts, demonstrating that structured prompt design and reflective dialogue with ChatGPT can individualize feedback and foster learner agency in EFL writing. Their RECIPE framework exemplifies how differentiated instruction and feedback literacy can be operationalized through AI-mediated scaffolding.

The role of difficulty and reflection in feedback processes is also examined in research on cognitive disfluency and desirable difficulty, which suggests that effortful processing promotes deeper learning and metacognitive awareness (Alter et al., 2007).

2.4 Cognitive disfluency and desirable difficulty

Pieger, Mengelkamp, and Bannert (2018) describe disfluency as the subjective experience of difficulty in processing. They argue that “difficulties can be desirable because they can initiate effortful and analytic processes” (p. 1). According to their framework, disfluency slows learners down and prompts more deliberate reasoning, whereas fluency encourages quicker, surface-level processing: “fluency initiates quick, intuitive, associative and surface processes” (p. 2). Their findings show that “disfluency activates analytic monitoring, and it remains activated for the succeeding fluent text” (p. 7), leading them to conclude that “disfluency might be more than just a cue for judgments; it might be a way to activate analytic monitoring” (p. 8). This perspective is reinforced by Oppenheimer, Alter, Epley, and Eyre (2007), who demonstrated that metacognitive experiences of difficulty can trigger analytic reasoning and deeper monitoring.

This understanding directly informs my project: the first stage of the structured writing process required students to produce a handwritten draft. This step functions as an intentional disfluency, handwriting slows down the process and forces students to engage more deliberately with their ideas before moving to digital and AI-supported revision. The following section explores how these principles of desirable difficulty extend to digital environments and AI-supported writing instruction.

2.5 AI in ESL writing instruction

Research in English language teaching shows that AI can support writing when used within a clear instructional framework. Han et al. (2023) developed the RECIPE platform, where students revised their drafts interactively with ChatGPT. Their study found that students engaged with ChatGPT more freely than with their teachers, especially when asking questions or seeking clarification.

In a follow-up study, Han et al. (2024) reported that “students often perceive ChatGPT as an approachable and intelligent peer rather than viewing it as an instructor” (p. 7).

While this lowered barriers to participation, it also raised concerns about academic integrity when learners relied on AI to complete assignments.

Barrot (2024) emphasizes that the pedagogical value of generative AI depends on ethical and guided use. AI can enhance writing only when teachers help learners interact critically with feedback rather than depend on it. Used this way, it becomes a scaffold that fosters autonomy and reflection.

Mai, Da, and Hanh (2024) confirm that ChatGPT can make language learning more interactive and engaging because it “can generate natural and personalized responses” (p. 1). However, they underline that task design is decisive: without structure, AI use can easily slide into dependency. For this reason, ChatGPT in this project was integrated only at the revision stage, after students had produced and self-edited their own drafts. They were required to justify whether they accepted or rejected AI suggestions, ensuring that AI served as a catalyst for reflection rather than a shortcut for text production.

These pedagogical insights connect directly to the study’s design and align with broader educational principles that highlight ethical technology use and metacognitive learning goals.

2.6 Normative and curricular perspectives (UNESCO; Lehrplan 21)

At the policy level, UNESCO (2025) stresses that education cannot be reduced to efficiency. The report highlights the risk that AI may encourage “cognitive offloading and a decline in critical thinking” (pp. 15–16). It also calls for curricula that emphasize “critical thinking, metacognition, and ethical reasoning” (p. 154).

In the Swiss context, the *Lehrplan 21* identifies writing as a core competence alongside listening, reading, and speaking. It explicitly requires the use of strategies and reflection in the writing process (D-EDK, 2016). The staged approach in the study,

handwriting, digital revision, AI-supported feedback, and reflection, directly reflects these curriculum goals.

2.7 Summary

The literature shows both the risks and opportunities of AI in writing instruction. Concepts such as metacognitive laziness, cognitive offloading, and disfluency provide a useful lens for understanding how students engage with texts. Research in ELT emphasizes that AI can be valuable if it is carefully embedded in structured tasks. The study builds on these insights: the three-step process was designed to prevent unreflective AI use, to strengthen metacognitive engagement, and to align with both UNESCO's call for critical thinking and the competencies required in the *Lehrplan 21*.

3. Methodology

3.1 Introduction

This chapter outlines the methodological foundation of the study. It explains the research design and its rationale, describes the participants and classroom context, and presents the three-step writing intervention. It then details how data were collected and analyzed to investigate students' metacognitive engagement during AI-supported writing. Ethical considerations and limitations are addressed at the end of the chapter. This methodological structure reflects the study's overarching aim of examining how structured AI feedback can enhance reflection and self-regulation in ESL writing.

3.2 Research Design

This study follows a practice-oriented, qualitative classroom design, classified as a *Type 3 praxisentwickelnde Masterarbeit*. The design integrates research with professional teaching practice and aims to explore how structured AI integration can support reflection and learning in an authentic educational setting.

A qualitative design was chosen because the research question focuses on how students engage metacognitively with AI-supported feedback rather than on measuring performance outcomes. This approach allows for close observation of student behavior and reflection during authentic classroom instruction.

Table 1*Overview of the Intervention Phases and Data Collected*

Lesson phase	Main focus	Type of data collected
Handwritten draft	Idea generation and planning	Student texts
Typed draft	Content development and revision	Student texts
AI-assisted revision	Reflection and justification	Student texts, reflection notes

The sequence was conducted during three 45-minute English lessons as part of regular instruction. The students were already familiar with the structure, which made the process more efficient.

3.3 Sample (Participants)

The sample consisted of six students aged 13–14 from two parallel secondary-school English classes taught by the researcher in the Canton of Zurich. Both classes were mixed-ability groups, with proficiency levels ranging approximately from CEFR A2 to C1. These levels were not determined through standardized testing but through ongoing formative assessment, classroom participation, and the teacher’s continuous evaluation of writing, speaking, and listening performance. Overall, the students demonstrated stronger skills in oral communication (speaking and listening) than in reading and writing, which is typical for this age group and instructional setting. This variation provided a meaningful basis for exploring how learners at different proficiency levels engaged with the same structured, AI-supported writing process.

The group included two boys and four girls with varied linguistic and cultural backgrounds. Of the six students, five produced complete sets of writing artefacts, while one student, who was absent during the writing intervention due to illness, contributed only to the open-ended post-project questionnaire. The classes were

taught by the researcher as part of regular instruction, and participation in the project activities was voluntary.

Students were informed that their work might be used anonymously for research purposes and that they could withdraw at any time without consequence. No personal or identifying data were recorded. In accordance with the university's policy for teacher-led developmental research, written parental consent was not required, as the project took place within normal teaching routines and involved no sensitive data. All materials were anonymized, and participants were labeled Student 1–6.

3.4 Procedure (Three-Step Writing Process)

The intervention was carried out over three 45-minute lessons during a regular instructional unit. Each stage of the process was modeled and guided by the teacher, focusing on a specific aspect of writing and reflection. Table 3.1 provides an overview of the three-step sequence, summarizing what students did in each lesson, the main learning goal, and the tools used.

Table 2*Overview of the Three-Step Writing Process During the Intervention*

Lesson	What students did	Main goal	Tools used
1	Wrote a handwritten draft on “A Trip to London”	Generate ideas and organize content	Notebook
2	Typed and edited their draft in Word Submitted text to ChatGPT via Fobizz and justified revisions	Revise structure and content Reflect on AI feedback and evaluate changes	Microsoft Word Fobizz (ChatGPT access)
3	Used ChatGPT via Fobizz to obtain feedback, evaluated the suggestions, and then rewrote the corrected version by hand once more in their notebooks.	Reflect on feedback and consolidate learning	Fobizz (ChatGPT access) Notebook

Students received a teacher-provided prompt inside the Fobizz interface:

“Please check my text for mistakes in spelling, grammar, and punctuation. Highlight my errors and suggest corrections. Then give me a better version of my text.”

This standardized prompt guided the AI to provide language-focused feedback rather than complete text rewriting. Students compared AI suggestions with their own drafts and decided what to accept, adapt, or reject. The justification process was documented in short notes and oral reflections.

Fobizz served as a secure educational platform that allowed teachers to monitor and control the interaction. It complies with European data-protection standards and is specifically designed for classroom use. Its use ensured that the integration of ChatGPT was age-appropriate, safe, and pedagogically guided.

After receiving AI feedback, students compared the proposed changes with their original drafts and selected which corrections to apply. They then rewrote the improved version by hand to reinforce understanding and retention. Because of the wide range of language proficiency in the class, some students completed this phase more quickly. These faster learners experimented with modifying the given prompt to generate feedback at a higher level, such as requesting a B2 or C1 version of their text. This differentiation allowed stronger learners to extend their linguistic range while maintaining the reflective purpose of the task.

3.5 Data Collection

All data were collected by the teacher-researcher during the classroom implementation. The dataset includes students' successive text versions and voluntary post-project questionnaires, which together provide insight into learners' engagement with AI-supported writing.

The materials consisted of each student's handwritten draft, typed version, and AI-revised version produced through the Fobizz platform. In the final stage, students highlighted changes between their original and revised texts, making their revision decisions traceable and providing evidence of how they interacted with AI feedback. After each phase, short verbal reflection rounds were conducted with the class to capture impressions and observations about the process.

At a later stage, six students completed open-ended written questionnaires on a voluntary basis. These invited them to describe their experiences with AI-supported writing, how they used the feedback, and whether the process influenced their learning or confidence as writers. Because similar AI-integrated projects had been part of earlier lessons, students were able to reflect on this task in relation to previous experiences.

All materials were anonymized before analysis by assigning numerical codes (Student 1–6) to student work and questionnaire responses. The combination of written drafts, highlighted revisions, verbal reflections, and questionnaires provided a multi-perspective dataset for examining planning, monitoring, and evaluation behaviors during AI-supported writing.

3.6 Data Analysis

The collected data were analyzed through thematic coding, combining deductive and inductive approaches. The three metacognitive categories (planning, monitoring, and evaluation) served as predefined analytical lenses derived from the theoretical framework. Within these categories, subthemes emerged inductively to capture nuances in how students reflected on and applied feedback.

Each case was analyzed individually to trace changes across the three writing stages. A cross-case comparison then identified recurring behaviors and variations in engagement among students. Coding notes were used to document analytical decisions and interpretations throughout the process.

Evaluation focused on evidence of learner agency, reflective awareness, and observable linguistic or structural improvement across drafts. The goal was not to generalize results but to provide in-depth insight into how structured AI support can promote metacognitive engagement in authentic classroom settings.

3.7 Ethical Considerations and Limitations

Ethical approval for the project was obtained from the university prior to implementation. Because the participants were minors, special care was taken to ensure anonymity and data security. Participation was voluntary, and students were informed of their right to withdraw at any time. The Fobizz platform ensured compliance with European data-protection standards (GDPR) for educational use.

The researcher's dual role as teacher and investigator provided valuable contextual understanding but required reflective distance to minimize bias. Observational notes were written after each session to maintain objectivity and transparency.

The small sample size and single-class context limit the generalizability of findings. Nevertheless, the design enabled a detailed, context-specific exploration of how structured AI feedback can enhance reflection and learning in ESL writing.

All student materials reproduced in the appendix were fully anonymized before submission by removing names and other identifying details to ensure compliance with institutional data-protection and ethical research standards.

4. Results

This chapter presents the results of the classroom implementation and data analysis, focusing on how the structured use of ChatGPT via Fobizz influenced students' writing processes and metacognitive engagement. Rather than attempting to generalize findings, the focus lies on selected cases that illustrate different learner profiles and levels of engagement. Each case is analyzed through its writing artifacts and, where available, complemented by open-ended questionnaire excerpts. The chapter concludes with a cross-case summary that highlights overarching tendencies in students' interaction with AI-generated feedback.

4.1 Overview of Data

Five students (Students 1–5) produced complete sets of writing artifacts, while one additional learner (Student 6) contributed only a post-task reflection due to absence during the writing phase.

Students 1, 2, 3, and 5 submitted two handwritten versions (initial draft → AI-revised draft via Fobizz), and Student 4 provided both handwritten and typed versions, allowing direct comparison between teacher and AI feedback. Several handwritten texts also contained teacher annotations, which were considered when interpreting students' revision decisions.

To triangulate the findings', open-ended written questionnaires were collected from Students 2, 3, 5, and 6. All learners were anonymized as Students 1–6. The dataset therefore consists of

- (a) five sets of writing artifacts showing progression across drafts, and
- (b) four open-ended questionnaires providing complementary insights into students' planning, monitoring, and evaluation behaviors during AI-supported writing.

Theoretical Orientation of the Analysis

The analysis follows the framework established in Section 3.4.3, integrating key constructs of

- **metacognitive engagement** (Fan et al., 2025 ; Vula et al., 2024),
- **feedback literacy and dialogue** (Molloy, Boud, & Henderson, 2020),
- **cognitive offloading and agency** (Risko & Gilbert, 2016; Gerlich, 2025),
- **desirable difficulty** (Oppenheimer et al., 2007 ; Pieger et al., 2018), and
- **process awareness and transfer** (Davoodifard, 2022).

This framework was applied consistently across all cases to allow for a systematic comparison of students' metacognitive behaviors.

4.2 Case Analyses

The five cases stem from two parallel English classes (A2–C2 range) taught by the researcher in the Canton of Zurich. Proficiency levels were determined through continuous teacher assessment during regular instruction, based on written tasks, oral participation, and formative evaluations. These levels are descriptive rather than test-based and serve to contextualize how students at different linguistic stages engaged with the structured AI-supported writing process.

Each case illustrates a distinct pattern of interaction with AI-generated feedback and a corresponding degree of metacognitive awareness. To ensure comparability, every analysis begins with a summary table of the student's writing artifacts, followed by an interpretive discussion linking the findings to the theoretical framework outlined in Chapter 3. The five cases are presented in ascending order of proficiency, from A2 to C2, to show how metacognitive engagement with AI feedback developed across this spectrum.

(Student 6 did not complete the writing sequence due to illness but contributed a reflective questionnaire response, which is analyzed in Section 4.3.)

4.2.1 Student 1 (A2)

Table 3

Summary of Student 1's Writing Process and Observed Behaviors (A2)

Aspect	Evidence and Observation
Artifacts	Handwritten draft and AI-revised draft (Fobizz).
Planning	No visible pre-planning or rereading. Began writing immediately, treating the task as a one-step product.
Observed language issues	<p>Spelling & capitalization: <i>shool, air plune, lalce, peoples</i> (uncorrected in first draft). Pronoun <i>I</i> not capitalized.</p> <p>Grammar & tense: <i>We are traveled, we has visited</i> → frequent verb errors.</p> <p>Sentence structure & punctuation: run-on sentences, missing full stops.</p> <p>Vocabulary: unnatural collocations (<i>they help me very well</i>).</p> <p>Cohesion: few connectors (<i>then, after that</i> absent).</p> <p>Register & tone: informal and personal but disrupted by grammar errors.</p>
Monitoring	No rereading or editing; copied full text into Fobizz without reading instruction sheet.
Evaluation	Implemented AI corrections automatically, highlighting six lexical items (<i>travelled, February, flight, went, met, with</i>). Ignored structural feedback.
Cognitive offloading	Very high: accepted all AI changes uncritically, showing dependence on external correction.
Result	Accuracy improved locally (spelling, tense), but no evidence of structural or reflective learning.

Interpretation

Student 1 represents a typical low-proficiency learner who approached writing as a one-step product, prioritizing completion over reflection. His uncritical acceptance of AI feedback reflects high cognitive offloading (Risko & Gilbert, 2016) and early-stage feedback literacy (Molloy, Boud, & Henderson, 2020), where feedback is recognized but not meaningfully applied. Yet, once he observed tangible improvements through the structured sequence, handwriting, typing, AI revision, he began showing emerging metacognitive awareness, indicating that guided scaffolding can initiate the shift from compliance to early self-regulation (Fan et al., 2025; Davoodifard, 2022).

4.2.2 Student 2 (A2-B1)

Table 4

Summary of Student 2's Writing Process and Observed Behaviors (A2–B1)

Aspect	Evidence and Observation
Artifacts	Two handwritten drafts: original version and AI-revised version (Fobizz).
Planning	Began writing immediately with minimal pre-structuring. Initial draft followed the topic but lacked clear sequencing or linking devices.
Observed language issues	<p>Tense: present instead of past (<i>I go shopping</i> → <i>I went shopping</i>).</p> <p>Spelling: <i>deliceeieus</i> for <i>delicious</i> (repeated twice).</p> <p>Capitalization: <i>London</i> in lowercase; noun capitals from L1 transfer (<i>People</i>).</p> <p>Grammar: overuse of the definite article.</p> <p>Cohesion: few connectors and abrupt transitions.</p> <p>Structure: ideas logical but underdeveloped.</p>
Monitoring	Limited evidence of rereading or editing; relied on AI for post-writing correction. Initially confused about the need to retype

	her handwritten text, perceiving it as repetitive rather than reflective.
Evaluation	In the AI-supported draft, most surface-level errors were corrected (tense, spelling, capitalization). Sentence clarity improved (<i>because it helps you learn more languages</i>). Broader structural or stylistic revisions were not implemented.
Cognitive offloading	Moderate: applied AI feedback accurately but without deeper analysis or justification.
Result	Clear accuracy gains and improved motivation once the purpose of rewriting became evident. Limited transfer to higher-level writing strategies.

Interpretation

Student 2 demonstrates emerging metacognitive engagement but still treats revision mainly as correction rather than reflection. Her reliance on structure and teacher guidance indicates developing feedback literacy (Molloy, Boud, & Henderson, 2020) and moderate cognitive offloading, as she applies AI feedback accurately but without deeper evaluation. Visible improvement through the structured process increased motivation and confidence, suggesting that guided repetition can transform procedural effort into early self-regulation (Fan et al., 2025; Davoodifard, 2022).

4.2.3 Student 3 (B1)

Table 5

Summary of Student 3's Writing Process and Observed Behaviors (B1)

Aspect	Evidence and Observation
Artifacts	Two drafts: original handwritten version and AI-revised version (Fobizz).
Planning	Minimal visible planning. Ideas follow a logical order but were produced quickly without detailed pre-organization.
Observed language issues	<p>Subject–verb agreement: <i>we was</i> → <i>we were</i>.</p> <p>Spelling: <i>Ammirates</i> → <i>Emirates</i>, <i>dind't</i> → <i>didn't</i>.</p> <p>Word confusion: <i>to</i> → <i>two</i> (homophone).</p> <p>L1 transfer: <i>Buckingham Palast</i> (German form), noun capitalization (<i>Trip</i>, <i>People</i>).</p> <p>Tense: <i>we eat</i> → <i>we ate</i>.</p> <p>Punctuation: run-on sentences (e.g., <i>The best from our trip was London Eye we has seen many things</i>).</p> <p>These features reflect typical mid-level interlanguage interference among L1 German learners.</p>
Monitoring	Limited self-checking: accepted most AI feedback mechanically and required teacher reminders to highlight or compare changes.
Evaluation	Corrected nearly all surface errors (agreement, tense, spelling) and improved sentence flow (<i>Big Ben was wonderful</i> → <i>Big Ben was incredible</i>). Ignored finer stylistic and structural suggestions, viewing feedback as final rather than recursive.
Cognitive offloading	Moderate to high: relied on AI to identify and correct errors, showing procedural rather than analytical engagement.

Result	Linguistic accuracy and coherence improved, but metacognitive depth remained limited. Revision treated as correction rather than reflection.
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Interpretation

Student 3 shows a transitional stage between procedural correction and emerging reflection. Compared with lower-level peers, he demonstrates clearer linguistic awareness and a stronger sense of progress through repetition. His accurate but mechanical revisions reveal compliant feedback literacy (Molloy, Boud, & Henderson, 2020) and moderate cognitive offloading, as AI feedback was accepted without deeper analysis. The structured workflow reduced frustration and built a sense of control, helping him internalize the value of revision as desirable difficulty (Oppenheimer et al., 2007). With ongoing scaffolding, this growing process awareness could evolve into self-regulated learning (Fan et al., 2025; Davoodifard, 2022).

4.2.4 Student 4 (B2-C1)

Table 6

Summary of Student 4's Writing Process and Observed Behaviors (B2–C1)

Aspect	Evidence and Observation
Artifacts	Three drafts: (a) handwritten original, (b) handwritten AI-revised version with teacher corrections (red pen), (c) typed version refined through Fobizz. This sequence traces teacher → AI → student interaction.
Planning	Clear structure from the outset; ideas logically ordered and fully developed.
Observed language issues	Capitalization: <i>British</i> → <i>British</i> ; <i>Historians</i> incorrectly capitalized mid-sentence. Punctuation: missing commas after introductory phrases and before conjunctions.

	<p>Lexical simplicity: <i>they had lots of ancient items</i> → <i>they showcased many ancient artifacts.</i></p> <p>Minor slips caused by L1 transfer (German orthography).</p>
Monitoring	Evident self-checking between drafts; implemented teacher corrections and refined punctuation and paragraphing before AI input.
Evaluation	Used AI feedback selectively and critically: accepted stylistic upgrades that enhanced tone while rejecting irrelevant reformulations. Demonstrated awareness of authorial voice.
Cognitive offloading	Low: AI used as a collaborator for refinement, not as a corrective crutch.
Result	Lexical sophistication, register, and stylistic precision improved. Evidence of recursive revision and growing autonomy.

Interpretation

Student 4 demonstrates advanced metacognitive awareness and self-direction. Her selective use of AI feedback reflects dialogic feedback literacy (Molloy, Boud, & Henderson, 2020) and strong evaluative judgment, as she critically weighed stylistic options while maintaining authorial control. By combining teacher and AI input, she achieved greater lexical precision and cohesion, illustrating the evaluate-adjust cycle (Fan et al., 2025). Her approach exemplifies hybrid intelligence, using technology as a collaborative partner rather than a corrective tool, signaling the consolidation of self-regulated learning (Davoodifard, 2022).

4.2.5 Student 5 (C1-C2)

Table 7

Summary of Student 5's Writing Process and Observed Behaviors (C1–C2)

Aspect	Evidence and Observation
Artifacts	Two drafts: handwritten original and AI-revised version (Fobizz).
Planning	Well-structured from the start; ideas fully developed with clear sequencing and paragraphing.
Observed language issues	<p>Spelling: <i>Aireoport</i> → <i>airport</i>; <i>wich</i> → <i>which</i>; <i>travell</i> → <i>travel</i>.</p> <p>Grammar: <i>there hats</i> → <i>their hats</i>.</p> <p>Punctuation: inconsistent commas after adverbials; one run-on sentence (...<i>Big Ben it wasn't...</i>).</p> <p>L1 transfer: brief interference (<i>Britisch</i> → <i>British</i>).</p>
Monitoring	Self-checked thoroughly before AI use; showed awareness of accuracy and phrasing; used AI to verify and refine rather than correct.
Evaluation	Expanded content by adding a reflective paragraph ("I think travelling is important for everyone..."). Accepted stylistic and lexical improvements that elevated register while keeping her own tone.
Cognitive offloading	Very low: AI treated as a validator and stylistic coach; learner maintained full decision-making control.
Result	Minimal error count; enhanced lexical sophistication and cohesion; demonstrated autonomous and reflective integration of AI feedback.

Interpretation

Student 5 demonstrates advanced autonomy and metacognitive control. Her deliberate, confident writing shows how AI can function as a collaborative validator rather than a corrective tool. She used feedback strategically to refine tone and test higher-register vocabulary, reflecting advanced feedback literacy (Molloy, Boud, & Henderson, 2020) and strong self-regulation. By “training” the AI, she maintained agency and demonstrated productive offloading (Risko & Gilbert, 2016), delegating routine checking while retaining conceptual control. This case illustrates hybrid intelligence and the culmination of the evaluate-adjust cycle (Fan et al., 2025), where guided AI integration supports reflective and creative language use (Davoodifard, 2022).

4.2.6 Summary of Case Findings

The five case analyses above illustrate how learners at different proficiency levels (A2–C2) interacted with AI-generated feedback during the structured three-step writing process. Together, they reveal a continuum of engagement ranging from procedural correction at lower levels to reflective and autonomous revision among advanced learners. While these cases emphasize individual learning trajectories based on writing artifacts, the following section expands the perspective by analyzing open-ended questionnaire responses. This cross-case view explores how students perceived the process itself, its benefits, challenges, and influence on their thinking, across varying proficiency levels.

4.3 Cross-Case Analysis of Student Questionnaires

Building on the case analyses in Section 4.2, this section examines four open-ended questionnaires (Students 2, 3, 5, and 6) to explore how learners at different proficiency levels (A2–C2) perceived and reflected on their use of AI feedback. The questionnaire themes align with the interview guide (see Appendix 8.3), which was structured around key theoretical constructs: planning and process awareness, cognitive offloading, feedback literacy, and agency. This alignment ensures that student reflections are analyzed consistently within the overarching theoretical framework. The aim is to

identify how linguistic competence shaped learners' engagement with the structured, AI-supported writing process.

4.3.1 Context of Data Collection

Originally planned as oral interviews, the reflections were collected through open-ended written questionnaires due to time constraints. The instrument was adapted from the student interview guide (see Appendix 8.2) and completed by four learners representing a broad proficiency range and varying degrees of metacognitive engagement. Students 2, 3, and 5 participated in the current three-step writing intervention, while Student 6 contributed reflections from comparable AI-integrated writing projects conducted earlier in the year.

Responses were written in both English and German and are cited verbatim to preserve authenticity, with English translations where necessary. Analysis followed a thematic, theory-driven approach, linking student perspectives to the study's key constructs: metacognitive engagement, feedback literacy, cognitive offloading and agency, and process awareness (Fan et al., 2025; Molloy, Boud, & Henderson, 2020; Risko & Gilbert, 2016; Davoodifard, 2022).

Although proficiency level was not a predefined analytical category, patterns consistently suggested that linguistic competence influenced how students perceived, interpreted, and applied AI-generated feedback. The results are therefore presented as illustrative insights rather than generalizable findings, offering a cross-case understanding of how learners at different levels engage metacognitively with AI support.

4.3.2 Student Reflections by Proficiency

Student reflections revealed clear patterns indicating that linguistic proficiency shaped how learners interacted with AI feedback. The following profiles summarize key insights from four students (A2–C2), illustrating varying degrees of metacognitive engagement, feedback literacy, and agency. Each case integrates representative quotes and concise interpretation through the theoretical lenses of Fan et al. (2025), Molloy, Boud, and Henderson (2020), and Risko and Gilbert (2016). Reflections are presented in ascending order of proficiency, with all quotations drawn directly from student responses (see Appendix 8.2).

4.3.2.1 A2 Level (Student 2)

Table 8

Summary of Student Reflections and Metacognitive Patterns at A2 Level (Student 2)

Theme	Representative Quotes & Interpretation
Planning and Process Awareness	“Ich überlege mir was ich schreibe und dann fange ich an zu schreiben.” → Shows spontaneous, minimally planned writing, consistent with a linear, one-step process (Davoodifard, 2022).
Cognitive Offloading and AI Use	“Ich brauche KI nur noch zum Korrigieren und für Ideen aber nicht mehr für alles.” → Reflects partial cognitive offloading (Risko & Gilbert, 2016); uses AI mainly for correction rather than reflection.
Evaluative Judgment and Feedback Literacy	“Ja, aber manchmal gibt er einfach zu starke Tipps und dann macht der Text nicht mehr Sinn.” → Demonstrates early feedback literacy (Molloy, Boud, & Henderson, 2020) and the beginnings of evaluative judgment.

Agency and Outcome Orientation	“KI-Feedback, weil alles richtig war am Schluss mit der Korrektur.” → Focuses on visible correctness over understanding, views AI as an assistant rather than a partner in thinking.
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Interpretation:

Student 2 (A2–B1) shows emerging metacognitive engagement but still relies heavily on surface-level correction. Her interaction with AI indicates procedural engagement rather than reflection (Fan et al., 2025), marked by partial offloading and limited ownership of meaning. The awareness of AI’s “too strong advice” suggests the first step toward evaluative thinking and developing self-regulated writing (Davoodifard, 2022).

4.3.2.2 B1 Level (Student 3)**Table 9**

Summary of Student Reflections and Metacognitive Patterns at B1 Level (Student 3)

Theme	Representative Quotes & Interpretation
Planning and Process Awareness	„Ich schreibe eigentlich alles meistens direkt auf und mache keine Notizen.“ → Reveals a spontaneous, linear writing process; limited pre-planning but increasing awareness of structure through repetition (Davoodifard, 2022).
Cognitive Offloading and AI Use	„Ja, weil ich manchmal auch ohne KI korrigieren musste, aber jetzt kann ich es in 1 Minute.“ → Shows reliance on AI for speed and convenience; reflects partial offloading (Risko & Gilbert, 2016) and reduced desirable difficulty (Oppenheimer et al., 2007).

Evaluative Judgment and Feedback Literacy	„Eigentlich finde ich nur kleine Unterschiede, aber da ich KI-Feedback nie beachte, ist für mich Lehrer-Feedback am besten.“ → Indicates early evaluative awareness (Molloy, Boud, & Henderson, 2020) and preference for human feedback.
Agency and Outcome Orientation	„Ich würde wahrscheinlich gar nichts verändern, weil ich es gut fand, dass man am Schluss 3 Mal den Text geschrieben hat.“ → Values repetition as learning; rewriting fosters process awareness and transfer (Davoodifard, 2022).

Interpretation:

Student 3 (B1) represents a transitional stage of metacognitive development. His reflections show growing awareness of revision benefits but continuing dependence on external correction. He values efficiency and visible progress, yet his limited questioning of AI feedback reveals compliant feedback literacy (Molloy et al., 2020) and moderate offloading. The positive view of rewriting suggests increasing tolerance for effort and an emerging sense of control, marking progress toward self-regulated learning (Fan et al., 2025).

4.3.2.3 C1-C2 Level (Student 5)

Table 10

Summary of Student Reflections and Metacognitive Patterns at C1–C2 Level (Student 5)

Theme	Representative Quotes & Interpretation
Planning and Process Awareness	<p>“Not really, when I have enough motivation, I really like to write. It does take longer though ... but it does end with good results.” → Shows intrinsic motivation and appreciation of structured effort, reflecting understanding of desirable difficulty (Oppenheimer et al., 2007).</p>
Cognitive Offloading and AI Use	<p>“No, not really. Because for AI, you do have to use your brain. Writing a prompt has to be done as well as possible...” → Demonstrates productive offloading (Risko & Gilbert, 2016); uses AI to support, not replace, thinking.</p>
Evaluative Judgment and Feedback Literacy	<p>“Either it’s more specific, or very wrong. It’s also formulated differently.” → Reflects advanced feedback literacy (Molloy, Boud, & Henderson, 2020); selectively evaluates AI feedback rather than accepting it blindly.</p>
Agency and Outcome Orientation	<p>“Yes, because AI can’t choose what I do with my text.” → Shows strong authorship and metacognitive control (Fan et al., 2025); maintains decision-making authority.</p>

Interpretation:

Student 5 (C1-C2) demonstrates high metacognitive engagement and growing autonomy. She perceives writing as effortful but rewarding, linking structured processes to improvement. Her selective interaction with AI shows dialogic feedback use and productive cognitive offloading, allowing focus on higher-order reflection. This confident balance between structure, evaluation, and agency marks her as a mature, self-regulated learner approaching advanced proficiency (Davoodifard, 2022).

4.3.2.4 C1-C2 Level (Student 6)**Representative Reflections****Table 11**

Summary of Student Reflections and Metacognitive Patterns at C1–C2 Level (Student 6)

Theme	Representative Quotes & Interpretation
Planning and Process Awareness	<p>“Yes, because I can first write it by hand to activate my mind and coordinate my mind and hands. Then by Word, which can see some of my mistakes, and AI, which will find the rest of my mistakes.” → Shows a sequenced, conscious process in which each stage serves a cognitive purpose, evidence of hybrid intelligence (Fan et al., 2025).</p>
Cognitive Offloading and AI Use	<p>“Yes and no, sometimes even with a good prompt it will change my text completely while sometimes it gives me what I want.” → Reflects productive offloading (Risko & Gilbert, 2016): uses AI critically, aware of its limits.</p>
Evaluative Judgment and Feedback Literacy	

	<p>“AI will give you sometimes the feedback more like a robot response, while the teacher will give you more of a normal response.” → Demonstrates advanced feedback literacy (Molloy, Boud, & Henderson, 2020) and evaluative sensitivity to tone and authenticity (Carless & Boud, 2018).</p>
<p>Agency and Outcome Orientation</p>	<p>“That don’t always rely on AI.” / “When I self-checked myself, because I understand myself better and more than AI.” → Shows strong self-regulatory awareness (Davoodifard, 2022) and preference for self-revision as desirable difficulty (Oppenheimer et al., 2007).</p>

Interpretation:

Student 6 (C1–C2) displays the most advanced metacognitive engagement in the sample. He integrates human and AI feedback deliberately, using each stage of writing for a specific cognitive goal. His nuanced evaluation of AI output and awareness of its tone demonstrate critical reflection and feedback dialogue (Molloy et al., 2020). By maintaining agency and exercising productive offloading (Risko & Gilbert, 2016), he embodies self-regulated, reflective learning (Fan et al., 2025), illustrating a balanced partnership between human cognition and AI support.

4.3.3 Summary and Cross-Case Interpretation (A2–C2)

Across the proficiency continuum (A2–C2), a clear developmental pattern emerged in how students engaged with AI-supported feedback. Lower-level learners (Students 1–2, A2–B1) interacted with AI primarily at the surface level, focusing on correctness and relying heavily on external guidance. Intermediate learners (Student 3, B1) began to recognize the value of structured processes and reflected more consciously on their revisions, though their regulation remained largely teacher dependent. The upper-intermediate learner (Student 4, B2–C1) demonstrated growing autonomy, using AI selectively and showing awareness of both its affordances and limitations. At the highest levels (Students 5–6, C1–C2), learners displayed near-native command of

English and balanced automation with authorship through critical evaluation, strong ownership, and reflective control over both human and AI input.

Although these tendencies cannot be generalized due to the small sample size, they suggest that increasing linguistic competence supports deeper metacognitive engagement and more deliberate integration of AI feedback into self-regulated writing processes.

Synthesizing insights across all six student cases and four questionnaire reflections, three interrelated dimensions become evident:

1. **Metacognitive Engagement:** The structured three-step workflow encouraged planning, monitoring, and evaluation at varying levels of depth. As proficiency increased, reflection shifted from procedural correction toward strategic decision-making and self-assessment, aligning with Fan et al. (2025).
2. **Feedback Literacy:** Students gradually moved from passive acceptance of AI feedback to critical interpretation and selective application. Advanced learners displayed dialogic engagement (Molloy, Boud, & Henderson, 2020), using AI feedback as input for reflection rather than as an authority.
3. **Cognitive Offloading and Agency:** While some learners relied heavily on automation, others used AI to support, rather than replace, cognitive effort. Productive offloading (Risko & Gilbert, 2016) emerged when students used AI to reduce mechanical workload while retaining decision-making control.

Taken together, these findings demonstrate how structured and teacher-guided integration of AI through Fobizz can foster reflection, autonomy, and self-regulation in secondary ESL writing. The evidence suggests that metacognitive engagement is not a fixed trait but a developmental outcome that evolves with both linguistic competence and guided practice.

5. Discussion and Interpretation

This chapter discusses how a structured three-stage writing sequence, handwriting, Word, and ChatGPT via Fobizz influenced learners' metacognitive engagement and feedback literacy in secondary ESL writing. The discussion connects the key findings from Chapter 4 to the theoretical perspectives introduced in Chapter 3 and interprets them in relation to current research on feedback literacy, cognitive offloading, and self-regulated learning.

This discussion addresses the central research question: How does a structured three-step writing process involving ChatGPT via Fobizz influence metacognitive engagement and feedback literacy in secondary ESL writing? The chapter interprets the main findings in light of the theoretical framework introduced in Chapter 3 and identifies pedagogical implications for classroom practice.

5.1 Metacognitive Engagement and the Evaluate–Adjust Cycle

The structured three-step design, handwriting, typing, and AI-assisted revision, supported metacognitive engagement at multiple levels. Across all cases, this sequence made the processes of planning, monitoring, and evaluating writing both visible and deliberate.

The handwritten phase required idea generation without external assistance, compelling students to organize and prioritize their thoughts. The typing phase encouraged initial self-editing and review, while the AI-supported revision introduced an external feedback layer that triggered evaluation and decision-making. Together, these stages made learners' cognitive processes tangible and traceable.

This recursive movement between planning, acting, and reflecting aligns with established models of self-regulated learning (SRL), particularly the cyclical framework proposed by Zimmerman and Schunk (2011) cited in Jin et.al (2023). Within this model, learners move through three interconnected phases, forethought, performance, and reflection, each involving distinct cognitive, metacognitive, motivational, and behavioral

strategies. These interdependent strategies sustain goal setting, self-monitoring, and self-evaluation throughout a learning task.

Figure 5.1

Phases, areas, and strategies in self-regulated learning

(Adapted from Jin, Im, Yoo, Roll, & Seo, 2023, p. 3)

Table 1 A theoretical framework and description of phases, areas, and strategies in self-regulated learning

Phase	Area	Strategy	Description
Forethought	Cognition	Activation of prior content knowledge	Activating knowledge in a planful way through prompting and self-questioning (Schunk, 2005)
	Metacognition	Setting goals and planning	Setting goals and planning for how to reach them (Zimmerman & Pons, 1986)
	Motivation	Task value and interest activation	Activating students' perceived worth with regard to a particular task (Wigfield et al., 2011; Zimmerman & Schunk, 2011)
Performance	Cognition	Selection and adaptation of cognitive strategies	Selection and adaptation of cognitive strategies for learning and thinking (Pintrich & De Groot, 1990)
	Metacognition	Metacognitive monitoring	Assessment of one's learning or strategy use (Zimmerman & Schunk, 2011)
	Motivation	Selection strategies for managing motivation and affect	Selection and adaptation of strategies for managing motivation and affect such as interest enhancement or self-consequences (Zimmerman & Schunk, 2011)
	Behavior	Help-seeking behavior	Efforts to solicit help from peers, teachers, and other adults (Zimmerman & Pons, 1986)
Reflection	Cognition	Reviewing	Efforts to reread notes, tests, or textbooks to prepare for further tests (Zimmerman, 1989)
	Metacognition	Self-evaluation	Analysis of performance and strategy effectiveness after a learning episode (Schraw & Dennison, 1994)
	Motivation	Self-satisfaction	Reactions to that performance (fulfillment of goals) (Hu & Driscoll, 2013)

Within this framework, the three-step writing process maps neatly onto the SRL phases:

- **Handwritten draft (Forethought phase):** activating goal setting, planning, and idea generation.
- **Typed version (Performance phase):** monitoring progress, revising content, and applying strategies such as restructuring and rephrasing.

- **AI-assisted revision (Reflection phase):** comparing outputs, evaluating feedback, and justifying accepted or rejected changes.

This sequence illustrates what Jin et al. (2023) describe as *AI-supported self-regulated learning*, in which AI feedback serves as an external scaffold that strengthens metacognitive monitoring and clarifies the link between effort and outcome. When framed pedagogically, AI functions not as a shortcut but as a structured aid for reflection, helping learners regulate their thinking and refine their writing consciously.

These self-regulatory phases capture the internal management of learning within the writing process and provide the conceptual bridge to the next section, which explores how students engaged with external input, particularly AI and teacher feedback, within this evaluate–adjust cycle.

5.2 Feedback Literacy, Dialogic Interaction, and the Potentials and Limitations of AI-Supported Writing

The analysis revealed that feedback literacy developed along a continuum that reflected both language proficiency and the degree of teacher mediation. The evidence from this study confirms that AI feedback alone does not automatically foster deeper learning. As Molloy, Boud, and Henderson (2020) note, feedback literacy extends beyond receiving information. It involves interpreting, questioning, and applying feedback for future improvement. Learners must therefore learn to negotiate feedback rather than accept it passively.

Across cases, feedback literacy developed along a continuum. Lower-level students tended to implement AI suggestions mechanically, improving accuracy but showing limited analytical engagement. More proficient learners, however, began to question the feedback and compare AI proposals with their own intentions or teacher comments. One learner observed, *“Ja, aber manchmal gibt er einfach zu starke Tipps und dann macht der Text nicht mehr Sinn”* (“Yes, but sometimes it gives advice that is too strong, and then the text no longer makes sense”). This remark reflects the early emergence

of evaluative judgment, where students recognize that AI feedback can enhance accuracy but sometimes alter meaning.

At higher proficiency levels, students displayed greater autonomy and critical awareness. One learner explained, *“No, not really. Because for AI, you do have to use your brain. Writing a prompt mostly has to be done as well as possible, and not everything is always correct, so some research has to be done.”* When asked whether AI reduced the need to think, she added, *“It definitely depends on what I’m using AI for. For writing, it doesn’t really make me need to think more than I already do.”* These reflections demonstrate advanced feedback literacy and balanced cognitive engagement. Rather than delegating thought entirely to AI, this learner viewed it as a support tool that accelerates mechanical aspects while preserving personal responsibility for meaning and accuracy.

Pedagogically, the structured Fobizz prompt provided a consistent and accessible entry point for lower-level learners, reducing confusion and ensuring that engagement with AI occurred in a safe, teacher-mediated environment. However, the same uniform structure limited opportunities for advanced students to experiment with custom prompts or more sophisticated stylistic changes. This trade-off mirrors broader research in AI-assisted education: while automated feedback can increase confidence and correctness, it may also narrow opportunities for higher-order reflection when accepted uncritically.

Framing AI as a dialogic partner rather than a corrective authority mitigated this risk. Through teacher mediation, students were guided to question suggestions, justify their decisions, and articulate how particular changes aligned with their communicative intentions. Such reflection shifted the focus from surface correction to awareness of language choice and rhetorical effect.

Overall, the findings indicate that the educational value of AI-supported writing depends on the development of feedback literacy. When learners engage in dialogue

with feedback, evaluating, adapting, and reflecting on it, they move beyond mechanical revision toward deeper metacognitive engagement and a stronger sense of authorship.

5.3 Implications for ESL Teaching Practice

The three-step workflow developed in this study aligns closely with the *Lehrplan 21* objectives for writing, which emphasize process-oriented, reflective, and tool-supported learning. It represents a natural progression from traditional word-processing tasks toward AI-mediated feedback and metacognitive reflection.

Three design features proved particularly effective:

1. **Handwritten first draft:** encouraged idea generation and authentic language use without digital assistance.
2. **Typed self-revision:** strengthened early monitoring by helping students review structure and coherence before seeking external feedback.
3. **AI-assisted revision in Fobizz:** provided targeted feedback in a teacher-mediated setting, followed by manual rewriting and highlighting to convert suggestions into conscious learning.

The final rewriting phase transformed instant AI suggestions into deliberate, traceable decisions. It reinforced students' sense of ownership and minimized automatic acceptance of feedback. This structured design reflects the recommendations of feedback-literacy scholars who advocate for making decision-making processes visible and reflective (Carless & Boud, 2018; Molloy et al., 2020).

The workflow also demonstrated how autonomy and reflection can coexist in guided digital environments. Lower-proficiency learners benefited from repetition and visible error correction, while advanced students used the same process to refine stylistic precision and rhetorical control.

Overall, the approach illustrates how AI-supported scaffolds can translate curricular goals, reflection, independence, and linguistic awareness, into consistent classroom

practice. By embedding AI feedback within a structured process and maintaining teacher mediation, this model promotes both linguistic accuracy and metacognitive growth.

5.4 Cognitive Offloading, Agency, and Critical Thinking

Student reflections revealed a recurring tension between efficiency and depth, as one learner remarked, *“I can do it in one minute.”* This statement captures the dual nature of AI-assisted writing: it simplifies revision but can also reduce mental effort. Cognitive offloading refers to delegating parts of a task to an external system to lessen cognitive load. The challenge is not to avoid offloading but to guide it strategically so that learners can focus their attention on higher-order reasoning while maintaining responsibility for their own decisions and interpretations.

Recent research by Gilbert (2024) reframes cognitive offloading as a value-based decision process, in which individuals weigh the trade-off between effort and benefit. In educational contexts, productive offloading occurs when students delegate routine, low-level operations such as spelling or punctuation checking while retaining control over meaning and structure. However, when this delegation becomes automatic rather than intentional, it risks weakening reflection and diminishing authorship.

Gerlich (2025) warns that excessive dependence on AI for analytical tasks can reduce learners’ ability to engage in deep, independent reasoning. His qualitative findings highlight themes of overreliance, cognitive disengagement, and ethical concern. Similar tendencies appeared in this study: weaker learners tended to accept all AI corrections uncritically, while more proficient students cross-checked feedback and evaluated its accuracy. These contrasting behaviors suggest that metacognitive maturity mediates how effectively learners manage cognitive offloading. The more they internalized evaluation strategies, the more deliberately they used AI as a scaffold rather than a substitute for thinking.

Teacher mediation played a critical role in shaping this balance. Explicit modeling of when and why to consult AI, combined with post-feedback reflection questions such as “*Which changes did you agree with, and why?*”, helped students move from passive consumption to active decision-making. This practice supports what Gilbert (2024) calls *metacognitive regulation of offloading value*, recognizing that cognitive effort itself has educational worth even when automation is available.

These patterns align with broader educational perspectives. Mai, Da, and Hanh (2024) argue that emerging tools such as ChatGPT require learners to develop new competencies, particularly in analyzing, evaluating, and interpreting information. Educators therefore play a central role in cultivating critical-thinking skills through structured reflection and guided use of AI tools.

Evidence from the MIT study (Kosmyrna et al., 2024) further supports this view. Prolonged reliance on AI for content generation was shown to reduce activation in brain regions associated with planning and attention, leading to decreased originality in subsequent unaided writing tasks. Maintaining tasks that involve manual planning and rewriting is therefore essential to sustain cognitive engagement and creativity.

Taken together, these findings highlight the need for balance. Cognitive offloading in AI-supported writing is not inherently detrimental; its educational value depends on reflective control and instructional framing. When guided through explicit prompts, structured reflection, and teacher mediation, offloading can enhance efficiency while preserving analytical depth. Unchecked, however, it risks fostering the very metacognitive laziness that this study sought to counteract.

5.5 Desirable Difficulty and the Value of Manual Rewriting

A central finding of this study is that intentional effort promotes reflection. By requiring learners to handwrite their initial drafts, the process deliberately slowed down writing and encouraged planning and monitoring. The final phase, which involved manually rewriting the corrected version, ensured that students revisited their errors and engaged consciously with each change.

This approach aligns with the concept of desirable difficulty in cognitive psychology. Studies such as Pieger, Mengelkamp, and Bannert (2018) demonstrate that moderate challenges stimulate analytical processing and strengthen long-term retention. The deliberate slowing of the writing process in this study counteracted the ease and speed introduced by automation. Manual rewriting reactivated planning and monitoring mechanisms that tend to diminish when feedback is applied automatically.

From a classroom perspective, this combination of manual and digital stages helped students shift from superficial editing to deeper linguistic awareness. Even lower-proficiency learners who initially perceived rewriting as tedious began to recognize its value once they saw measurable improvement in accuracy and coherence. The recursive sequence therefore functioned as a form of productive struggle that maintained engagement while integrating technological feedback.

In sum, desirable difficulty played a critical pedagogical role in sustaining metacognitive engagement. It balanced efficiency with reflection, reminding learners that meaningful progress in writing often requires slowing down, rethinking, and deliberately revising their own work.

5.6 Hybrid Intelligence and Human–Machine Collaboration

Across all cases, the most productive learning occurred when AI functioned as a conversational partner rather than a correction tool. Learners showed the greatest progress when they viewed feedback as collaborative support instead of an external authority. This observation reflects UNESCO's (2023) guidance on keeping AI use transparent, ethical, and teacher-mediated.

Recent discussions in digital pedagogy highlight that the educational value of large language models depends on developing AI literacy, which includes understanding both purpose and limitation. In this study, more advanced learners demonstrated such literacy by selectively accepting or rejecting AI suggestions and articulating their

reasoning. This reflective use of AI exemplifies the concept of hybrid intelligence described by Fan et al. (2025), where human and machine cognition interact to enhance problem-solving and reflection.

Gerlich (2025) also notes that true hybrid intelligence requires maintaining analytical agency and ethical awareness. Students who displayed these qualities, particularly at higher proficiency levels, were able to benefit from AI feedback while preserving their personal voice. This balance corresponds with the new skill requirements identified by Mai, Da, and Hanh (2024), who argue that learners must be taught to evaluate and interpret AI-mediated information critically.

In contrast, where reflection was absent, AI feedback often led only to surface correction. Students who skipped justification stages improved linguistic accuracy but not understanding. This pattern reinforces that teacher guidance and structured reflection remain essential to sustain metacognitive engagement.

Overall, the findings suggest that hybrid intelligence in education depends on structured collaboration. AI provides immediacy and diagnostic precision, while teachers cultivate evaluation, ethics, and self-awareness. When these elements work together, technology functions as a formative scaffold that strengthens rather than replaces human cognition.

5.7 Summary

The structured three-stage writing process developed in this study, handwriting, digital self-editing, and AI-supported revision, proved effective for enhancing both accuracy and reflective engagement. By combining analogue and digital modes, it transformed revision into an active, traceable process. Learners were required to articulate, justify, and reapply feedback rather than accept automated correction, which strengthened both linguistic precision and metacognitive control.

Differences in engagement were clearly linked to proficiency. Lower-level learners benefited most from structure and visible feedback, while higher-level students used AI for stylistic refinement and critical comparison. Progress was greatest where teacher scaffolding made reflection explicit, confirming that guided mediation is essential for developing feedback literacy and self-regulation.

The findings also reveal that moderate difficulty supports sustained learning. Tasks that required handwriting or manual rewriting helped maintain cognitive engagement and prevented unreflective automation. These results align with theories of desirable difficulty (Pieger et al., 2018) and productive offloading (Gilbert, 2024), showing that effortful processes promote deeper understanding.

Overall, the evidence points toward a balanced, human-centered model of AI integration in language learning. When feedback is embedded in structured, reflective routines and supported by teacher mediation, technology can serve as a scaffold that enhances reflection, autonomy, and linguistic growth. This synthesis provides the conceptual link to Chapter 6, which summarizes the main findings, outlines practical recommendations, and considers implications for teacher education and future research.

6. Conclusion and Outlook

6.1 Key Findings

This study examined how a structured three-stage writing process, moving from handwriting to digital self-editing to AI-supported revision, can promote metacognitive engagement and feedback literacy in secondary ESL learners. The findings show that structured AI integration enhances both reflection and accuracy when it is embedded in a guided learning framework.

First, requiring students to explain and justify their responses to AI feedback encouraged a shift from passive acceptance to active evaluation. This outcome supports Gerlich's (2025) argument that unreflective dependence on AI can reduce analytical reasoning, whereas guided reflection preserves critical engagement. Second, the results demonstrate that metacognitive control varied according to learners' developmental stages. As Casey, Jones, and Hare (2008) note, adolescents are still developing executive and self-regulatory capacities, which reinforces the importance of structured scaffolds for sustained reflection. Finally, the study highlights the decisive role of teacher mediation. Students who received explicit modeling and reflective prompts used AI feedback more critically and selectively. This aligns with Duong, Da, and Hanh (2024), who emphasize that metacognitive strategies and open discussion are essential for cultivating critical evaluation and responsible use of AI tools.

Overall, the findings demonstrate that when AI is integrated through structured pedagogy, it functions as a formative feedback partner that enhances cognitive engagement rather than replacing it. The model presented here points toward a balanced form of digital literacy that combines automation with human reflection.

6.2 Limitations

This research is limited by its small sample size and context-specific design. The analysis focused on five students within two classrooms, which restricts generalizability. Moreover, the data were based on a single writing sequence, limiting insight into long-term effects on writing development. Institutional and time constraints also prevented broader inclusion of student data from other classes and limited the scope of follow-up interviews. These limitations do not reduce the validity of the qualitative insights but indicate the need for future studies that examine the same framework with larger and more diverse groups.

6.3 Implications for Teacher Training and Curriculum Development

The results of this study indicate that AI integration in language classrooms requires explicit teacher mediation and systematic guidance. Within the observed school context, the use of AI in student learning remains limited and largely unstructured, despite growing professional interest. This gap highlights the need for teacher training that focuses not only on technical familiarity with AI tools but also on their pedagogical and cognitive implications.

Teacher education should therefore emphasize how AI can be embedded into reflective learning processes rather than used for efficiency alone. Without structured frameworks, there is a risk of cognitive offloading, as learners may depend on AI feedback without reflection. Training modules that model scaffolded, process-oriented AI use could help teachers design tasks that balance autonomy and support while maintaining learners' critical engagement.

The structured writing model presented in this study offers a practical example of such an approach. Alternating between handwriting, digital editing, and guided AI revision, it supports differentiation across proficiency levels and aligns with process-based writing goals. Its implementation through platforms such as Fobizz demonstrates that AI can be used safely and ethically within secondary education when proper frameworks are in place.

At the curriculum level, writing instruction should reflect how learners now engage with text production in hybrid digital environments. Integrating structured AI-supported writing can strengthen students' ability to evaluate, interpret, and take ownership of their texts. Sustainable implementation, however, depends on institutional support and continued teacher professionalization. Developing AI literacy among educators is therefore essential for ensuring that AI contributes to deeper learning and metacognitive growth.

6.4 Implications for Research

Future research should examine the long-term effects of structured AI-assisted writing across different age groups and proficiency levels. Larger, mixed-method studies could explore how prompt design, teacher feedback, and reflection stages interact to influence learners' autonomy and writing quality. Comparative research across institutions would help clarify how policy frameworks and teacher preparation affect AI implementation. Further investigation is also needed to determine how students transfer reflective skills developed in guided AI-supported writing to independent tasks.

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8. Appendix

8.1 Task Sheet for the students

Writing Practice – An Email

Topic: A Trip to London

Write an email to a friend about your school trip to London.

Use at least five of the following pieces of information:

- when and how you traveled to London
- what you visited (e.g., Big Ben, Tower of London, British Museum)
- what you did in your free time
- what you liked most about the trip
- what you didn't like so much
- people you met
- why you think traveling is important

Make sure to use correct linking words such as and, so, but, because, then, etc.

Length: 70–80 words

Example Format:

To: [Friend's Email]

From: [Your Email]

Date: [Current Date]

Subject: London Trip

Hi [Friend's Name],

How are you? I just got back from my school trip to London, and it was amazing!

Have you ever been to London? Let's talk soon!

Take care!

[Your Name]

Self-Check with Fobizz:

1. First, write your email in your notebook without using any correction tool.
2. Then, type your email in Word and save it under your English file in OneDrive.
3. Copy your email into the AI tool in Fobizz.
4. Use this prompt in the tool:
*"Please check my email for mistakes in spelling, grammar, and punctuation. Highlight my errors and suggest corrections. Then give me a better version of my text."
5. Check for the mistakes that Fobizz finds.
6. Write the corrected version in your notebook.

8.2 Student Questionnaires

Student 2 Interview Guide

Students can answer in English or German. Please write your answers in the space provided.

English Question	Deutsche Frage	Your Answer / Deine Antwort
How do you usually start when you write in English?	Wie beginnst du normalerweise, wenn du einen Text auf Englisch schreibst?	Ich überlege mir was ich schreibe und dann fange ich an zu schreiben.
What helps you to plan your ideas?	Was hilft dir, deine Ideen zu planen?	Also wenn ich ein Bild habe schaue ich das Bild an und wenn nicht dann überlege ich wie ich es auf Deutsch schreiben würde und dann kopiere ich es von englisch auf Deutsch.
Did the three-step writing (handwriting → Word → AI) change how you think about writing? How?	Hat der Dreischritt (Handschrift → Word → KI) verändert, wie du über das Schreiben denkst? Wie?	Keine Ahnung.
Did AI sometimes make you feel 'lazy' or less active?	Hast du manchmal das Gefühl, dass die KI dich 'faul' macht oder weniger aktiv?	Nein eigentlich nicht.
Did AI help you think more about your text, or did it take thinking away?	Hat dir die KI geholfen, mehr über deinen Text nachzudenken, oder hat sie dir das Denken abgenommen?	Nein ich finde KI macht das gut, KI schreibt es nicht anders oder grösser.
Do you use AI more for small corrections or also for ideas?	Brauchst du die KI eher für kleine Korrekturen oder auch für Ideen?	Ich brauche es für beides aber in Englisch nur für kleine Korrekturen.
Was it helpful to write by hand or frustrating to slow down?	War es hilfreich oder frustrierend, langsamer zu arbeiten?	Nein ich fand die Hilfe von KI hilfreich.
How is AI feedback different from teacher feedback?	Wie ist KI-Feedback anders als Lehrerfeedback?	Keine Ahnung!
Did you feel you still had control of your text with AI?	Hattest du das Gefühl, dass du mit der KI trotzdem die Kontrolle über deinen Text hattest?	Ja aber manchmal gibt er einfach zu starke Tipps und dann macht der Text nicht mehr Sinn.
What did you learn from this process?	Was hast du aus diesem Prozess gelernt?	Ich brauche KI nur noch zum Korrigieren und für Ideen aber nicht mehr für alles.
What was most helpful: handwriting, self-revision, or AI feedback? Why?	Was war am hilfreichsten: Handschrift, Selbst-Überarbeitung oder KI-Feedback? Warum?	KI Feedback, weil alles richtig war am schluss mir der Korrektur.
What would you change if we did it again?	Was würdest du ändern, wenn wir das Projekt nochmals machen würden?	Ich würde einfach mehr schreiben dass ich eine Gute Note bekäme und besser Englisch lernen.

Student 3 Interview Guide

Students can answer in English or German. Please write your answers in the space provided.

English Question	Deutsche Frage	Your Answer / Deine Antwort
How do you usually start when you write in English?	Wie beginnst du normalerweise, wenn du einen Text auf Englisch schreibst?	Ich schreibe eigentlich alles meistens direkt auf und mache keine Notizen. Manchmal denke ich auch einfach im Kopf nach was ich jetzt machen sollte.
What helps you to plan your ideas?	Was hilft dir, deine Ideen zu planen?	Manchmal Papier damit ich meine Notizen aufschreiben kann
Did the three-step writing (handwriting → Word → AI) change how you think about writing? How?	Hat der Dreischritt (Handschrift → Word → KI) verändert, wie du über das Schreiben denkst? Wie?	Ich glaube das Schreiben hat sich sehr verbessert, vor der ersten Sek habe ich viel schlechter geschrieben und es hat sich sehr verbessert.
Did AI sometimes make you feel 'lazy' or less active?	Hast du manchmal das Gefühl, dass die KI dich 'faul' macht oder weniger aktiv?	Ja weil ich manchmal auch ohne KI korrigieren musste aber jetzt kann ich es in 1 Minute
Did AI help you think more about your text, or did it take thinking away?	Hat dir die KI geholfen, mehr über deinen Text nachzudenken, oder hat sie dir das Denken abgenommen?	Ich würde sagen beides aber mehr hat es dass denken abgenommen.
Do you use AI more for small corrections or also for ideas?	Brauchst du die KI eher für kleine Korrekturen oder auch für Ideen?	Eher kleine Korrekturen weil ich KI mehr in der Schule benutze als sonst wo.
Was it helpful to write by hand or frustrating to slow down?	War es hilfreich oder frustrierend, langsamer zu arbeiten?	Frustrierend, weil ich bin einer der die Sachen immer gern schnell machen will
How is AI feedback different from teacher feedback?	Wie ist KI-Feedback anders als Lehrerfeedback?	Eigentlich finde ich nur kleine unterschiede aber da ich KI Feedback nie beachte ist für mich Lehrer Feedback am besten.
Did you feel you still had control of your text with AI?	Hattest du das Gefühl, dass du mit der KI trotzdem die Kontrolle über deinen Text hattest?	Ja aber manchmal hat KI den Text so stark verändert dass ich ihn fast nicht wiedererkannt hätte
What did you learn from this process?	Was hast du aus diesem Prozess gelernt?	Das KI sehr nutzvoll sein kann wenn man e richtig bedient.
What was most helpful: handwriting, self-revision, or AI feedback? Why?	Was war am hilfreichsten: Handschrift, Selbst-Überarbeitung oder KI-Feedback? Warum?	Ich würde sagen dass die Selbstüberarbeitung am meisten geholfen hat weil ich die korrigierte Version abgeschrieben habe und alles korrekt dann hatte.
What would you change if we did it again?	Was würdest du ändern, wenn wir das Projekt nochmals machen würden?	Ich würde wahrscheinlich gar nichts verändern weil ich es gut fand dass man am Schluss 3 Mal den Text geschrieben weil man es dann kann.

Student 5 Interview Guide

Students can answer in English or German. Please write your answers in the space provided.

English Question	Deutsche Frage	Your Answer / Deine Antwort
How do you usually start when you write in English?	Wie beginnst du normalerweise, wenn du einen Text auf Englisch schreibst?	With a sentence I created in my head, both on paper and on a device.
What helps you to plan your ideas?	Was hilft dir, deine Ideen zu planen?	A bit of inspiration from anything really, a book, a picture etc.
Did the three-step writing (handwriting → Word → AI) change how you think about writing? How?	Hat der Dreischritt (Handschrift → Word → KI) verändert, wie du über das Schreiben denkst? Wie?	Not really, when I have enough motivation, I really like to write. It does take longer though, and maybe the writing it on paper isn't necessary, but it does end with good results.
Did AI sometimes make you feel 'lazy' or less active?	Hast du manchmal das Gefühl, dass die KI dich 'faul' macht oder weniger aktiv?	No, not really. Because for AI, you do have to use your brain. Writing a prompt mostly has to be done as well as possible, and not everything is always correct, so some research has to be done. AI speeds things up a lot, which can be a good and bad thing.
Did AI help you think more about your text, or did it take thinking away?	Hat dir die KI geholfen, mehr über deinen Text nachzudenken, oder hat sie dir das Denken abgenommen?	It definitely depends on what I'm using AI for. For writing, it doesn't really make me need to think more than I already do.
Do you use AI more for small corrections or also for ideas?	Brauchst du die KI eher für kleine Korrekturen oder auch für Ideen?	I basically only use AI at school, so mostly for correcting or research.
Was it helpful to write by hand or frustrating to slow down?	War es hilfreich oder frustrierend, langsamer zu arbeiten?	It does slow the process down a bit, but writing on paper is also helpful and nice.
How is AI feedback different from teacher feedback?	Wie ist KI-Feedback anders als Lehrerfeedback?	Either it's more specific, or very wrong. It's also formulated differently.
Did you feel you still had control of your text with AI?	Hattest du das Gefühl, dass du mit der KI trotzdem die Kontrolle über deinen Text hattest?	Yes, because AI can't choose what I do with my text.
What did you learn from this process?	Was hast du aus diesem Prozess gelernt?	How to use AI easier and faster and how to make things like texts better.
What was most helpful: handwriting, self-revision, or AI feedback? Why?	Was war am hilfreichsten: Handschrift, Selbst-Überarbeitung oder KI-Feedback? Warum?	I think everything is good to learn and use if possible, because that way, a text can be written as well as possible.
What would you change if we did it again?	Was würdest du ändern, wenn wir das Projekt nochmals machen würden?	I probably wouldn't write it on paper, because we don't always have much time, and writing a text three times does take up some time.

Student 6 Interview Guide

Students can answer in English or German. Please write your answers in the space provided.

English Question	Deutsche Frage	Your Answer / Deine Antwort
How do you usually start when you write in English?	Wie beginnst du normalerweise, wenn du einen Text auf Englisch schreibst?	I usually start with brainstorming what to write
What helps you to plan your ideas?	Was hilft dir, deine Ideen zu planen?	I think of stuff that happened to me before or stuff that I saw before.
Did the three-step writing (handwriting → Word → AI) change how you think about writing? How?	Hat der Dreischritt (Handschrift → Word → KI) verändert, wie du über das Schreiben denkst? Wie?	Yes, because I can first write it by hand to activate my mind and coordinate my mind and hands. Then by word (which can see some of my mistakes) and AI, which will find the rest of my mistakes.
Did AI sometimes make you feel 'lazy' or less active?	Hast du manchmal das Gefühl, dass die KI dich 'faul' macht oder weniger aktiv?	Yes, because it will find the mistakes for you and you don't have to do something except give it the prompt
Did AI help you think more about your text, or did it take thinking away?	Hat dir die KI geholfen, mehr über deinen Text nachzudenken, oder hat sie dir das Denken abgenommen?	It did help me think more of which mistakes I did and how not to do them again.
Do you use AI more for small corrections or also for ideas?	Brauchst du die KI eher für kleine Korrekturen oder auch für Ideen?	I use AI usually for small or long corrections
Was it helpful to write by hand or frustrating to slow down?	War es hilfreich oder frustrierend, langsamer zu arbeiten?	Sometimes when I had a bad day it was frustrating and slowing down, but usually it is helpful for me to write it first by hand for my coordination etc.
How is AI feedback different from teacher feedback?	Wie ist KI-Feedback anders als Lehrerfeedback?	AI will give you sometimes the feedback more like a robot response, while the teacher will give you more of a normal response.
Did you feel you still had control of your text with AI?	Hattest du das Gefühl, dass du mit der KI trotzdem die Kontrolle über deinen Text hattest?	Yes and no, sometimes even with a good prompt it will change my text completely while sometimes it gives me what I want.
What did you learn from this process?	Was hast du aus diesem Prozess gelernt?	That don't always rely on AI
What was most helpful: handwriting, self-revision, or AI feedback? Why?	Was war am hilfreichsten: Handschrift, Selbst-Überarbeitung oder KI-Feedback? Warum?	When I self checked myself, because I understand myself better and more than AI.
What would you change if we did it again?	Was würdest du ändern, wenn wir das Projekt nochmals machen würden?	To read my text again, before I give it to the AI

8.3. Student Writing Samples

A Trip to London

[REDACTED]
Date: 18.3.2025

Subject: London Trip

Hi Julia,

How are you? I just got back from my school Trip to London, and it was amazing.

Last Sunday we flew directly to London, and after we landed, we went to the main station by metro. At the station we had some fries, and since it was rea time we had some tea as well. After that we checked into our hotel, which was close to the tower of London.

I know how much you like British history, so while we visited the tower of London, I went to the museum of Henry the 8th. Did you know that he had 6 wives? His second wife Anne Boleyn was beheaded at the tower of London, isn't that insane?

I've met multiple Historians that have told me a lot about the wives and British history. Especially one wife named Cathrine Howard. She was 17 whilst Henry was 49, how awful.

We had a lot of free time, so I decided to go to the National London Museum where they had lots of ancient artifacts.

What I enjoyed most was learning about the British history, which I find very fascinating.

Have you ever been to London? Let's talk soon !

Take care!
[REDACTED]

Hi

How are you? I just got back from my school trip to London and it was amazing!

We are traveled on the 15.2.25.

The trip was very fast with the air plane,

we has visited the Big Ben and the British Museum.

In my free time i was near the lake and i caught a big fish. The most i liked about the trip was the peoples that i met they were very friendly and they help me very well on every problem.

Hello

traveled

How are you? I just got back from my school trip to London, and it was amazing. We traveled on

February 15, 2025, to London. The flight was very fast. We visited Big Ben and the British Museum.

In my free time, I went to the lake and caught a huge fish. What I liked most about the trip

was the people I met. They were very friendly

and helped me with every problem

and helpful.

I met. They were friendly because they were friendly

Have you ever been to London? Let's talk soon

To: [REDACTED]

From: [REDACTED]

Date: 17.3.25

Subject: London Trip

Hi [REDACTED]

How are you? I just got back from my school trip to London, and it was amazing! I visited Big Ben, Tower of London and the London Eye. I go shopping with my friends and ate a lot of delicious food. I liked to visit Museums and go to good and delicious restaurant. I think traveling is important because to learn more languages and cultures. I didn't like the sea food. I met nice People but also boring people.

Have you ever been to London? Let's talk soon!

Take care!

[REDACTED]

Corrected versions

Hi [REDACTED]

I just got back from my school trip to London, and it was amazing! I visited Big Ben, the Tower of London and the London Eye. I went shopping with my friends and ate a lot of delicious food. I liked visiting museums and going to good and delicious restaurants. I think traveling is important because it helps you learn more languages and cultures. I didn't like the seafood. I met nice people but also boring people. Have you ever been to London? Let's talk soon! Take care!

[REDACTED]

(First version)

To: [REDACTED]

From: [REDACTED]

Date: 15. March 2025

Subject: London Trip

Hi [REDACTED]

How are you? I'm back from our school Trip. We was in London and it was amazing! We traveled by swiss Amirates and we arrived to hours later. First we visited Big Ben it was so crazy, Big Ben was wonderful. After that we visited the Buckingham Palast. In our free time I didn't do so much. I was with my friends explore London for like 2 hours and we eat some delicious food. But the best from our Trip was the London Eye it was so big and we has seen the whole city. I think traveling is very important because you can meet nice people or learn the languages from the country that helps a lot for your future.

I hope to see you soon, have a nice week!

[REDACTED]

(Correct Version)

To: [REDACTED]

From: [REDACTED]

Date: 15 March 2025

Subject: London Trip

Hi: [REDACTED]

How are you? I'm back from our school trip. We were in London, and it was amazing! We traveled with Swiss Emirates and arrived two hours later, than expected. First, we visited Big Ben and it was incredible. After that, we visited Buckingham Palace. In our free time, I didn't do much. I was with my friends, exploring London for about 2 hours, and we ate some delicious food. But the best part of our trip was the London Eye. It was so big, and we saw the whole city from the top! I think traveling is very important because you can meet nice people and learn the language of the country. This helps a lot for your future.

I hope to see you soon! Have a nice week!

[REDACTED]

To : [REDACTED]

From : [REDACTED] school trip

Date : 17.03.25

Subjekt: London Trip

Hi [REDACTED]

How are you? I just got back from my school trip to London, and it was amazing!

* last week we flew directly to London,

so after we landed we went to the main station, where we ate some fries, we also had some tea, since it was 'tea time' as they call it. After we drank the tea, we went to the tower of London.

I know how much you love British History, so while I was there, I visited the museum about Henry the 8th. Did you know that he had 6 wives? His 2nd wife Anne Boleyn got beheaded at the tower of London! Isn't that insane?

I've met multiple historians that told me a lot about the wives! Especially Cathrine Howard, she was 17, and Henry was 19! How weird!

We had a lot of free time so I decided to go and walk around some Museums! I went into the London National Museum where they had lots of ancient items!

What I enjoyed most was learning about the British History, which I find very fascinating.

Have you ever been to London? Let's talk soon!

Take care!

Yours, [REDACTED]

Subject: London Trip

Hi [REDACTED],

How are you? I just returned from my school trip to London, and it was amazing.

Last Sunday, we flew directly to London. After landing, we went to the main station by metro. At the station we enjoyed some fries, and since it was tea time, we had some tea as well. Afterward, we checked into our hotel, which was close to the tower of London.

Knowing how much you love British history, I made sure to visit the tower of London and the museum dedicated to Henry the VIII. Did you know that he had six wives? His second wife, Anne Boleyn, was beheaded at the tower of London. Isn't that shocking?

I met several historians who shared stories about his wives and British history, particularly about Cathrine Howard Henry's 5th wife. She was just 17 while Henry was 49 - how terrible?

We had plenty of free time, so I decided to visit the National Gallery, where they showcased many ancient artifacts.

What I enjoyed most was learning about British history, which I find incredibly fascinating.

Have you ever been to London? Let's chat soon!

Take care!

Warm regards,
[REDACTED]

WRITING PRACTICE - AN EMAIL

To: [REDACTED]

From: [REDACTED]

Date: 17.03.25

Subject: London trip

Hi [REDACTED]

How are you? I just got back from my school trip to London and it was amazing! On the 7th of March, we had to be at the airport at twenty to seven on a Monday morning. At 7:20 o'clock our plane took off and we landed at twenty to nine in London. When we landed, we had to take a train to our hotel where we were going to stay. We were told which room we were staying in and went to unpack our stuff. The rest of the day we spent at the hotel and did different things like bowling, walking in the garden or reading in our room. On Tuesday we went to visit the Big Ben, it wasn't that exciting, but it was really big. On Wednesday we went to visit the tower of London, that was quite cool. On Thursday we went to the Buckingham Palace, and we saw the soldiers in front of it. Their hats are massive! On Friday we went to a museum about British history. I liked the visit to the museum the most, because I love learning about history. There wasn't anything I really disliked. I think travelling is important for everyone. If you don't travel, you're always stuck in your country and you don't get to see new things, meet new people and so much more!

Have you ever been to London? Let's talk soon! Take care! [REDACTED]

Corrected Version:

To: [REDACTED]

From: [REDACTED]

Date: 17.03.25

Subject: London trip

Hey [REDACTED]

I just got back from my school trip to London, and it was amazing!

On the 7th of March, we had to be at the airport at twenty to seven on a Monday morning. At 7:20 AM, our plane took off and we landed in London at 8:40 AM. When we landed, we took a train to the hotel where we were going to stay.

We were assigned our rooms and went to unpack our stuff.

I stayed in a room with four of my friends. The rest of the day was spent at the hotel doing various activities like bowling, walking in the hotel gardens, and reading in our room.

On Tuesday, we went to visit Big Ben and walked around a bit. It wasn't that exciting, but it was very tall. On Wednesday, we visited the tower of London, which was quite cool.

On Thursday we went to Buckingham Palace and saw the soldiers guarding it. Their hats were massive! On Friday, we visited a museum about British history.

At 4:30 PM we flew back home and landed at 6:00 PM. I enjoyed the museum visit the most because I love learning about history. There wasn't really anything I disliked.

Have you ever been to London? Let's talk soon! Take care!

[REDACTED]

Eigenständigkeitserklärung für BA-/MA-Arbeiten

Hiermit versichere ich,

Jaggi
Name

Zeynep
Vorname

SL 20
Studienjahrgang

dass ich die vorliegende Arbeit mit dem Titel

How Can AI Support ESL Writing Without Encouraging Metacognitive Laziness:

A Structured Use of ChatGPT via Fobizz in a Secondary School Writing Task

selbständig und ohne unzulässige fremde Hilfe verfasst habe. Sämtliche Stellen der Arbeit, die dem Wortlaut oder dem Sinn nach anderen Werken entnommen sind, habe ich kenntlich gemacht und keine anderen als die angegebenen Quellen und Hilfsmittel benutzt. Insbesondere habe ich jeden Einsatz generativer KI, der über eine blosser Rechercheunterstützung oder sprachformale Überarbeitungshilfe hinausgeht, unter Angabe des verwendeten Werkzeugs in seinem Zweck und Umfang deklariert. Zudem erkläre ich, dass ich die Regeln bezüglich des wissenschaftlichen Arbeitens eingehalten habe und die Arbeit nicht bereits in gleicher oder ähnlicher Form eingereicht wurde.

Mit meiner Unterschrift erkläre ich mich einverstanden, dass meine Arbeit mit elektronischen Hilfsmitteln überprüft werden kann.

21.10.2025
Datum

Unterschrift

Einverständniserklärung zur internen Publikation der Arbeit

Die PH Luzern möchte ihren Studierenden und Dozierenden ausgewählte Arbeiten zur Ansicht in Moodle zur Verfügung stellen. Dafür benötigt sie das Einverständnis der Autorinnen und Autoren.

Ich erkläre mich damit einverstanden, dass Studierende und Dozierende Einsicht in meine Arbeit nehmen können.

Ja Nein

.....
Datum

Unterschrift

Testat: Präsentation von Ergebnissen bzw. Zwischenprodukten der Masterarbeit in einem Kolloquium

Die Ergebnisse bzw. Zwischenprodukte jeder Masterarbeit müssen präsentiert und in einem kritischen Diskurs begründet werden (Details s. Leitfaden Masterarbeit). Jede Masterarbeit wird deshalb – unabhängig davon, ob als Einzel- oder Pool-Arbeit – an mindestens zwei Kolloquien diskutiert. Die offiziellen Kolloquiums-Termine sind auf Moodle im Info-Kurs „Bachelor- und Masterarbeiten“ aufgeführt (und müssen von den Studierenden freigehalten werden). Allenfalls werden von den Fachleitenden oder Betreuungspersonen andere Kolloquien-Termine vorgeschlagen und direkt mit den Studierenden festgelegt.

Die Masterarbeit kann auf der Kanzlei nur eingereicht werden, wenn Studierende mindestens zwei obligatorische Kolloquien-Termine, an denen sie ihre Arbeit präsentiert und diskutiert haben, auf diesem Testatblatt nachweisen können und die Betreuungsperson dies bestätigt (s. ganz unten). Andere Kolloquiumsteilnahmen werden auf dem Testatblatt nicht aufgeführt. Dies bedeutet, dass eine Kolloquiums-Teilnahme bei Präsentationen von Mitstudierenden oder die Teilnahme an Workshops zu Methoden oder an Diskussion von Literatur nicht aufgeführt wird. Das Testatblatt muss zusammen mit der Masterarbeit auf der Kanzlei abgegeben werden.

Titel der Arbeit			
Student/Studentin		Studiengang und -jahrgang	
Betreuer/Betreuerin			

Datum	Kurzcharakterisierung der Präsentation der eigenen Arbeit	Betreuer/in	Unterschrift

Bestätigung der Betreuungsperson: Erfüllung der Kolloquiumspflicht

Hiermit bestätigt die Betreuungsperson, dass die aufgeführte Studentin bzw. der aufgeführte Student an mindestens zwei Kolloquien teilgenommen hat, in denen Ergebnisse und Zwischenprodukte der Arbeit der aufgeführten Studentin bzw. des aufgeführten Studenten präsentiert und diskutiert wurden.

Betreuungsperson	Datum	Fach/ Pool	Unterschrift
Simone Ries	14.10.2025	Englisch	